

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DESIGN AND *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION OF SUBLINGUAL
TABLETS OF ZOLPIDEM TARTRATE****Botla Manohar¹, Pranay Renukuntla², Daniel Kothapally²**¹Vaagdevi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bollikunta, Warangal²Sri Shivani College of Pharmacy, Muluguroad, Warangal**Article Received:** September 2022 **Accepted:** September 2022 **Published:** October 2022**Abstract:**

The sublingual tablets of zolpidem were prepared by direct compression method using Ludiflash, Prosolv HD 90, and F-melt with varying concentrations. The developed sublingual tablets were evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters. The results of all formulations were found within the pharmacopeia limits. The optimized formulation (F9) with F-melt (25%) showed the maximum percentage of drug release was 98.79% in 30 min and used for short-term treatment of insomnia. The disintegration time, drug content, wetting time, and water absorption studies were evaluated for all the formulations.

Keywords: Zolpidem, sublingual tablets, direct compression, and water absorption ratio

Corresponding author:**Botla Manohar,**

Mobile no: 9398021177

man.botla99@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article Botla Manohar *et al*, Design And In-Vitro Evaluation Of Sublingual Tablets Of Zolpidem Tartrate., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2022; 09(10).

1. INTRODUCTION:

The development of sublingual tablets of zolpidem (ZP) is a nonbenzodipiene that acts as a sedative-hypnotic agent and it was important in the aspect that it overcomes the patient's discomfort, particularly the elder people who feel difficulty swallowing, high dose and side effects that arise from oral conventional formulation tablets of a sedative-hypnotic drug ⁽¹⁾. Sublingual formulations are to be placed under the tongue and produce an immediate systemic effect by enabling the drug absorbed directly through the mucosal lining of the mouth beneath the tongue. The drug absorbed from the stomach goes to mesenteric circulation which connects to the stomach via the portal vein ⁽²⁾. Thus, absorption through the oral cavity avoids first-pass metabolism. Also, rapid onset of action can be achieved with the use of sublingual tablets ⁽³⁾. These are designed to dissolve in a small quantity of saliva. After the dosage form is placed in the mouth below the tongue, the patient should avoid eating, drinking, smoking, and possibly talking to keep the formulation in place. Swallowing of saliva should also be avoided since the saliva may contain dissolved drugs ⁽⁴⁾. The current research work is to develop novel formulations of sublingual tablets of zolpidem tartrate which is used to treat insomnia aimed at patients with difficulty starting sleep.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Materials

Zolpidem tartrate was obtained as a gift sample from Divis Laboratories, Hyderabad. Ludiflash, Prosolv HD 90, and F-melt were purchased from JRS Pharma. Avicel PH 101 was purchased from Hiranya Cellulose Products, Hyderabad. Talc and Magnesium stearate was from Neutron Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad. The orange flavor was procured from Gogia chemical industries Pvt Ltd, Noida. All other chemicals and reagents are analytical grade were used in the study.

2.2. Methods

2.1. Preparation of the tablet formulation by direct compression method

The sublingual tablets of zolpidem tartrate were prepared by direct compression technique ⁽⁵⁾. Accurately drugs were weighed and to this add ludiflash, prosolv HD 90, F-melt, and other excipients such as avicel PH 101, talc, and magnesium stearate were added. All the ingredients were passed through sieve no 60. Tablets were compressed by using 6mm flat punches on sixteen stations rotary tablet compression machine ⁽⁶⁾. The compositions of formulations are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Components used in sublingual tablet formulations

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Zolpidem tartrate	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
Ludiflash®	15	20	25	-	-	-	-	-	-
Prosolv HD 90®	-	-	-	15	20	25	-	-	-
F-melt®	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	20	25
Avicel PH 101	25	20	15	25	20	15	25	20	15
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Talc	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Orange flavour	Q.S								
Total weight (mg)	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50

2.2. Characterization of oral disintegrating tablets

2.2.1. Evaluation of pre-compression parameters

Angle of repose

The angle of repose was determined by using the funnel method. The powder was poured from a funnel that can be raised vertically until a maximum cone height (h) was obtained. The diameter of the heap (D) was measured.

Bulk density

Apparent bulk density was determined by pouring the pre-sieved drug excipient blend into a graduated cylinder and measuring the volume and weight as it is ⁽⁶⁾.

Tapped density

It was determined by placing a graduated cylinder containing a known mass of drug, excipient blend on mechanical tapping apparatus, which was operated for a fixed number of taps until the powder bed volume has reached a minimum. Using the weight of a blend in a cylinder and with the minimum volume occupied, the tapped density was computed ⁽⁷⁾.

Compressibility index and Hausner ratio

These were calculated by using the following equation. % Compressibility = $\{(\rho_t - \rho_b) / \rho_t\} \times 100$ and Hausner ratio = ρ_t / ρ_b .

2.2.2. Evaluation of post-compression tablets

Weight variation

Twenty (20) tablets were weighed randomly using an electronic balance and the average weight was determined. The individual tablets were weighed and compared with the average weight ⁽⁸⁾.

Hardness

The hardness of tablets was determined by using a Monsanto tablet hardness tester ⁽⁹⁾.

Friability

The Friability of ten tablets from each formulation was determined using the Roche friabilator. This device subjects the number of tablets to the combined effect of abrasions and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolves at 25 rpm dropping the tablets at a distance of 6 inches with each revolution. Pre-weighed sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator, which was then operated for 100 revolutions. Tablets were dusted and re-weighed ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Drug content uniformity

Ten tablets were finely powdered; quantities of the powder equivalent to 10 mg of zolpidem tartrate were accurately weighed, and transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask containing pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and allowed to stand for 5 hrs with intermittent shaking to ensure complete solubility of the drug. The mixture was made up to volume with buffer. The solution was suitably diluted and the absorption was determined by a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 242 nm. The drug concentration was calculated from the calibration curve ⁽¹¹⁾.

Wetting time and water absorption ratio

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish containing 6 ml of water. A tablet was put on the paper and the time required for complete wetting was measured. The wetted tablet was taken and weighed ⁽¹²⁾.

Thickness

Ten (10) tablets were taken randomly from each formulation and their thickness was measured using Vernier calipers ⁽¹³⁾.

Disintegration studies

In-vitro disintegration time for sublingual tablets was determined using the USP disintegration apparatus with pH 6.8 buffer as the disintegration medium ⁽¹⁴⁾.

In vitro drug release studies

The dissolution rate was studied by using USP type II apparatus at 75 rpm, pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, 900 ml was used as dissolution medium. The temperature of the dissolution medium was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. An aliquot of dissolution medium was withdrawn at a specific time interval and it was filtered. The absorbance of the filtered solution was checked by UV spectroscopy at 242 nm wavelength and drug content was determined from the standard calibration curve. The dissolution rate was studied for all designed formulations ⁽¹⁵⁾.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Evaluation of pre-compression studies

The pre-compression studies like bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner ratio, and angle of repose were determined for the prepared powder blend. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of pre-compression parameters

Formulations	Pre-compression parameters of powder blend (Mean \pm SD)				
	Angle of repose	Bulk density	Tapped density	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
F1	29.51 \pm 0.19	0.32 \pm 0.05	0.39 \pm 0.14	26.18 \pm 2.19	1.29 \pm 0.21
F2	30.18 \pm 0.25	0.29 \pm 0.13	0.31 \pm 0.17	15.35 \pm 1.24	1.35 \pm 0.74
F3	32.53 \pm 0.16	0.38 \pm 0.17	0.42 \pm 0.23	24.61 \pm 2.03	1.56 \pm 0.69
F4	28.64 \pm 0.21	0.41 \pm 0.19	0.37 \pm 0.19	29.05 \pm 1.85	1.24 \pm 0.27
F5	27.49 \pm 0.18	0.35 \pm 0.11	0.29 \pm 0.12	21.17 \pm 2.04	1.27 \pm 0.42
F6	29.81 \pm 0.24	0.32 \pm 0.09	0.41 \pm 0.27	21.62 \pm 1.42	1.41 \pm 0.29
F7	26.73 \pm 0.28	0.41 \pm 0.28	0.34 \pm 0.28	16.27 \pm 1.59	1.17 \pm 0.54
F8	28.17 \pm 0.23	0.39 \pm 0.26	0.28 \pm 0.15	21.13 \pm 1.74	1.20 \pm 0.47
F9	27.59 \pm 0.17	0.36 \pm 0.14	0.31 \pm 0.22	15.39 \pm 1.82	1.19 \pm 0.51

The powder blend evaluated for pre-compression studies' angle of repose was found in the range of 23.2° to 29.8°, this exhibits good flow properties. The results of Carr's index and Hausner's ratio were found within the limits. Among these formulations (F9) exhibits a good flow pattern.

The formulated sublingual tablets of zolpidem were evaluated for post-compression studies such as hardness, friability, thickness, weight variation, and content uniformity for all the formulations. The results were found to be within acceptable limits. The disintegration time, wetting time, and water absorption ratio was determined for all the developed formulations. The results are presented in Table 3.

3.2. Evaluation of post-compression studies

Table 3: Results of post-compression studies

Formulations	Post-compression parameters of sublingual tablets of zolpidem tartrate (Mean \pm SD)					
	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)	Disintegration time (Sec)	Assay (%)
F1	50.82 \pm 1.73	4.3 \pm 0.19	0.79 \pm 0.04	3.01 \pm 0.19	12.06 \pm 1.21	91.28 \pm 2.84
F2	54.16 \pm 2.04	4.2 \pm 0.14	0.61 \pm 0.09	2.64 \pm 0.23	11.39 \pm 1.74	95.37 \pm 3.65
F3	51.18 \pm 2.16	3.3 \pm 0.16	0.82 \pm 0.12	2.31 \pm 0.52	12.19 \pm 1.69	98.14 \pm 4.02
F4	55.31 \pm 1.29	4.8 \pm 0.21	0.67 \pm 0.18	2.59 \pm 0.49	13.04 \pm 1.27	96.01 \pm 2.75
F5	49.95 \pm 1.82	4.1 \pm 0.27	0.60 \pm 0.17	2.17 \pm 0.84	11.42 \pm 1.42	100.12 \pm 3.19
F6	52.47 \pm 2.48	3.9 \pm 0.29	0.81 \pm 0.13	3.29 \pm 0.91	14.59 \pm 1.29	94.81 \pm 2.65
F7	50.68 \pm 1.51	3.6 \pm 0.18	0.74 \pm 0.19	3.75 \pm 0.56	12.71 \pm 1.54	103.29 \pm 3.78
F8	56.29 \pm 1.74	3.9 \pm 0.26	0.63 \pm 0.15	4.12 \pm 1.04	13.29 \pm 1.47	99.85 \pm 3.89
F9	55.73 \pm 2.16	4.5 \pm 0.152	0.58 \pm 0.11	3.89 \pm 0.78	10.75 \pm 1.51	102.24 \pm 3.41

The results of the post-compression studies are within the limits. Friability studies of all formulations showed 0.58% to 0.82% which indicates the tablets are having good mechanical strength. The results of the hardness of the tablets were found to be 3.3 to 4.8 kg/cm². The assay results were found 91.28% to 103.29%. The thickness of the tablets was found between 2.17 mm to 4.12mm.

3.3. Evaluation of pH, wetting time, and water absorption studies

The pH, wetting time, and water absorption ratio of developed formulations were determined. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of evaluation parameters (Mean \pm SD)

Formulation codes	pH	Wetting time (Sec)	Water absorption ratio (%)
F1	8.62	48.5 \pm 2.05	81.9 \pm 3.05
F2	9.16	63.7 \pm 3.29	75.1 \pm 2.18
F3	8.29	59.1 \pm 3.14	86.4 \pm 2.73
F4	7.58	56.9 \pm 3.82	77.3 \pm 2.36
F5	9.36	61.4 \pm 3.21	91.6 \pm 3.94
F6	10.25	69.2 \pm 3.78	87.2 \pm 3.72
F7	9.41	54.1 \pm 2.05	74.5 \pm 2.49
F8	7.29	45.8 \pm 2.57	70.7 \pm 4.15
F9	8.95	42.6 \pm 2.19	65.4 \pm 3.12

The developed formulations were studied for pH, wetting time, and water absorption ratio. The optimized formulation (F9) showed a wetting time found to be 42.6 sec and the water absorption ratio was found to be 65.4%. So, based on the above results F9 formulation is considered an optimized formulation.

3.4. *In vitro* drug release studies

The formulations F1 to F3 were prepared by using ludiflash, the release was found to be 87.17%, 90.28%, and 92.35%. Formulations F4 to F6 were made by prosolv HD 90® and release was found to be 82.16%, 84.91%, and 86.17%. Formulations F7 to F9 were utilizing F-melt® and the percentage of drug release was found to be 92.71%, 95.23%, and 98.79% in 30 min respectively. Based on studies, 25% of F-melt® containing formulation (F9) showed the maximum amount of drug release of 98.79% in 30 min. The release studies results were shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1: *In vitro* release studies of sublingual tablets of zolpidem

F-melt-containing formulations showed faster release than other formulations. This rapidly wicks solvents into the particle to increase swelling and enhance the disintegration and dissolution of tablets.

3.5. Drug-excipients compatibility studies

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra of the drug, and the optimized formulation (F9) were recorded in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The results are shown in Fig 2.

Fig 2: FTIR spectra of zolpidem (A); Optimized formulation (F9)

4. CONCLUSION:

The present work was to develop sublingual tablets of zolpidem by using ludiflash, prosolv HD 90, and F-melt with various concentrations (15%, 20%, and 25%) on the disintegration time and drug release studies. The tablets were prepared by direct compression technique. The developed formulations evaluated and met the pharmacopoeial specifications for hardness, friability, weight variation, wetting time, water absorption time, pH, and assay. The optimized formulation (F9) containing 25% of F-melt showed the maximum amount of drug release of 98.79% in 30 min. The disintegration time was found to be 10.75 sec. The wetting time and water absorption ratio were evaluated and the results were found to be 42.6 sec & 65.4%.

5. REFERENCES:

- 1) Kornblum S.S, Stoopak S.B (1973). A new tablet disintegrating agent: crosslinked polyvinylpyrrolidone. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 62: 43-49.
- 2) Sandeepthi B, Lingaraj S Danki, G Sridhar Babu, B Vidyadhara (2015). Development and in-vitro evaluation of lovastatin tablets using floating drug delivery system. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(2): 918-931.
- 3) Perrais D, Ropert N (1999). "Effect of zolpidem on miniature IPSCs and occupancy of postsynaptic GABAA receptors in central synapses". *Journal of Neuroscience*. 19 (2): 578-88.
- 4) Koizumi K, Watanabe Y, Morita K, Utoguchi N, Matsumoto M (1997). New method of preparing high-porosity rapidly saliva soluble compressed tablets using mannitol with camphor: A subliming material. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*.152 (2); 127-131.
- 5) Richman M.D, Fox D, Shangraw R.F(1965).Preparation and stability of glyceryl trinitrate sublingual tablets prepared by direct compression. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 54(3):447-451.
- 6) GS Babu, DV Kumar, G Balakrishna, RR Naik and PS Malathy (2014). Development and *in vitro* evaluation of immediate release tablets of efavirenz. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 3(3); 56-65.
- 7) Bindal Rishabh, Indurkha Arpna (2021). Formulation and evaluation of ketorolac tromethamine mouth dissolving tablets. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 11(1);60-64.
- 8) G Sridhar Babu, D Venkatadri, D Vijay Kumar, ND Kumar and PS Malathy (2015). Preparation and evaluation of atorvastatin calcium porous tablets by sublimation technique. *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 5(1), 2139-2144.
- 9) Golla Chandra Mouli, B Agaiah Goud, J Subhash, B Mallikarjun and L Srikanth (2018). Design and evaluation of press-coated pulsatile delivery of doxofylline tablets. *Acta Scientific Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2(11); 58-62.
- 10) Gummadi Sridharbabu, Sujatha Ramavath, S

- Srinu Naik (2014). Formulation and evaluation of oral dispersible tablets of clopidogrel bi sulfate by solid dispersion method. *Indo American journal of pharmaceutical research*, 1(3); 12-18.
- 11) Shankar Avulapati, Anup Kumar Roy, KR Shashidhar, TR UgendarReddy (2011). Formulation and evaluation of taste masked and fast disintegrating losartan potassium tablets, *International Journal of Drug Development and Research*, 3(1); 12-20.
- 12) C. Patil and S. Das (2011). Effect of various super disintegrants on the drug release profile and disintegration time of Lamotrigine orally disintegrating tablets. *African J of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 5(1): 76-82.
- 13) Swathi Daram, Prabhaker Reddy Veerareddy, Raju Jukanti, Suresh Bandari (2011). Formulation and evaluation of Ketorolac Tromethamine fast dissolving tablets. *Scholars Research Library, Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 3(2); 97-103.
- 14) Chandramouli Golla, Subhash Jadav, P.S Raghu (2017). Formulation and characterization of oral disintegrating tablets of valsartan by sublimation and effervescence methods. *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8(4); 4374-4385.
- 15) Gummadi Sridharbabu (2014). Formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving tablets of carbamazepine by direct compression using super disintegrants. *International Journal of Science Letters*, 4(5), 432-436.